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Information Seeking Behaviour of Faculty Members of Maharishi University of Management and Technology in Bilaspur Chhattisgarh, India: A Study

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Abstract:

This study aims to explore the information needs, seeking behaviors, purposes for seeking information, and challenges encountered by faculty members working in Maharishi University of Management and Technology, Bilaspur (C.G.) India. A questionnaire was randomly distributed to faculty members, with 142 out of 200 participants responding.

The analysis revealed that the majority of faculty members prefer the World Wide Web as their primary source of information. Of the respondents, 55(38.73%) visited the library once a week, while 14(9.85%) never spent time in library. Majority of the respondents are seeking information for preparing lectures 78(54.92%) and updating knowledge 62(43.66%). 3(37.31%) respondents seeking the information for their research work. The study also found that

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the faculty commonly faced two issues: the unavailability of resources and the overwhelming amount of information encountered while searching on the World Wide Web.

Keywords: Information, seeking behaviour, respondent

1.1 Introduction:

In today's world, information is essential to every aspect of life. From birth, individuals require information for their growth and development, making it a crucial resource. Academics, including scholars, faculty members, and students, constantly seek up-to-date information from various media available in libraries. Resources such as encyclopaedias, journals, magazines, newspapers, handbooks, yearbooks, and newsletters play a significant role in delivering the latest information.

As Singh K.P. and Satija M.P. (2006) noted, information seeking is a human process that demands adaptive and reflective management of the actions taken by the seeker. With the advent of electronic information and digital resources like CDs, DVDs, and the vast array of content available on the World Wide Web, the way people seek and access information has evolved. The growth of information technology has profoundly impacted users' information seeking behavior. Today, both printed and electronic resources are utilized by individuals to obtain the information they need from a variety of sources.

Maharishi University of Management and Technology (MUMT):

Maharishi University of Management and Technology (MUMT), Mangla, Bilaspur (C.G) was established vide Chhattisgarh Private Universities (Establishment and Operations) (Amendment) Act 2018 and received the assent of Hon'ble Governor of C.G. on 13th April 2018 followed by publication of Chhattisgarh Gazette (Extraordinary) on 17th April 2018. The Statutes and Ordinances of the University were approved by the C.G. State Government on 14 October 2019.

The University has created requisite infrastructure, Hostel Facility, Wi-Fi Campus, well equipped laboratory, and Eco-friendly campus with playgrounds.

1.2 Literature review:

The surveys on information seeking behavior have been done in many studies. In this electronic information era World Wide Web will be the valuable sources for collecting information on various field from any part of the world.

Ramaiah and Shimray (2018) conducted a study to assess the services and facilities offered by the Muffakham Jat College of Engineering and Technology Library in Hyderabad. The study aimed to evaluate library usage, identify gaps in the library's collection, services, and facilities, explore the use of digital libraries, and assess the overall utilization of library resources. A structured questionnaire was used to survey 350 students. Based on the findings, it was recommended that the library should enhance its collection, digitize resources, add more textbooks, and extend its operating hours to improve services. Although the study intended to identify gaps, it was noted that users were generally satisfied with the collection. The study concluded that the library needs to improve its electronic facilities and offer new services to keep pace with changing times. However, the study lacked details on the levels of satisfaction with different services, suggestions for accessing these services, and whether the library implemented these suggestions. While the recommendations are practical, they lack statistical validation. For instance, examining the relationship between the efficient use of library services and users' characteristics (such as age, gender, education, and specialization) could add credibility.

Kondamudi, Kumar, and Tripathi (2018) conducted a study on users' perceptions of e-books at Jawaharlal Nehru University. The study's primary objectives were to assess users' awareness of e-books and understand how students, teachers, and research scholars at the university access, browse, and use them. The study employed a survey method using a questionnaire to investigate reading behavior and identify gaps in e-book usage. It targeted students (both undergraduate and post-graduate), research scholars, and faculty members. A notable aspect of this study was the formulation and validation of hypotheses using a non-parametric statistical method.

The study by Kumar and Chandrashekara 16 (2015) focuses on "Information seeking behaviour of library users at government first grade college, Kushal Nagar, Karnataka". The study is only based on faculty members (Library users) of the

college. The main objective of this study is to identify the information used by the users of First Grade College, preference for resources, the process adopted by Faculties for getting the information. On the basis of replies received by the users, the authors found that the majority of the users access information through the internet library. The users faced some problems such as low internet speed, failure of electricity, shortage of time, among others. The study also revealed that users prefer to consult their personal collections on priority basis. However, two major limitations of this study are:

(i) the sample size is much too small even for cross-tabulations; and (ii) without statistical validation, these findings lack credibility.

Kingkaew Patitungkho and Neela J. Despande (2005) conducted a study focusing on the “information-seeking behavior of faculty members at Rajabhat University in Bangkok”. The research aimed to understand how these faculty members search for and use information. The findings revealed that 82% of the respondents sought information primarily for lecture preparation, while 57% relied on textbooks as their main reference source. Additionally, a significant challenge identified by the majority of respondents was the unavailability of needed information.

Jeyaraman, Srinivasaragavan, and Dorisamy (2011) conducted a study on the information-seeking behavior of students and faculty members. The research revealed that most respondents prefer using textbooks for reading and reference books for additional information. Approximately 31% of those surveyed visit the library daily to access information resources. The study also found that 71% of respondents utilize the library primarily to consult reference books, while only 22% refer to newspapers. Additionally, 58% of respondents use the library to access non-book materials.

Muhammad Tahir, Khalid Mahmood, and Farzana Shafique (2008) conducted a survey examining the information needs and seeking behavior of Arts and Humanities teachers at the University of Punjab in Lahore, Pakistan. Their findings indicated that reference books are the most vital resources for teaching, while consultations with experts in the field are crucial for 3 research. The study highlighted that face-to-face interactions are the most common communication channel used by these educators.

In a separate case study, Muhammad Rafiq and Kanwal Ameen (2009) explored the information-seeking behavior and satisfaction of instructors at the National Textile University. Their research showed that books remain the most preferred resource for both teaching and research, followed by communication with colleagues and journal articles. The majority of respondents reported visiting the library twice a week.

Preeti Mahajan (2009) discovered through research that students often need guidance and training to effectively use library resources. Meanwhile, Rubina Bhatti (2009) investigated the information needs and seeking behavior of faculty members at Islamia University, Bahawalpur. Bhatti's study found that while all respondents used library resources for teaching, fewer used them for other purposes. More than half of the participants viewed colleagues as their primary informal information source. The study also noted issues such as difficulty finding materials on shelves, limited internet access, and a shortage of computers. Bhatti concluded that the effectiveness of library operations heavily depends on the library's collection choices.

Lastly, Shakeel A. Khan and Farzana Shafique (2011) surveyed college faculty in Bahawalpur, discovering that faculty members often prefer direct discussions with colleagues and friends for information. They tend to rely on printed resources and use personal collections or institutional libraries when in urgent need of information.

This study seeks to explore the information-seeking behavior of faculty members at private engineering colleges in and around Chennai. Since academicians rely heavily on the library for resources across various topics, it is essential that the library maintains a comprehensive collection of subject-specific books. The information-seeking behavior of faculty members can differ based on factors such as location, timing, the specific information needed, and available sources. Through this type of research, the expectations and needs of those seeking information can be better understood and addressed.

1.3 Objectives of the Study:

The following objectives are framed for this study.

1. To know the sources for resources and information;

2. To examine the information-seeking behavior, purpose of seeking information;
3. To determine the barrier meeting on seeking information, usage of internet, visiting the library and library services;
4. To find the sufficiency or insufficiency on the resources at the library;
5. To find the difficulties faced by the faculty members on seeking information.

1.4 Methodology:

A structured questionnaire was distributed among 200 faculty members who were randomly selected. Questionnaire distributed directly to the faculty members who were working in Maharishi University of Management and Technology (MUMT), Mangla, Bilaspur (C.G). Filled questionnaires were collected from 142 faculties only (i.e. 71%). The data obtained under various questions were analyzed and interpreted as below.

1.5 Analysis and Interpretation:

Minimum specified chi-square value and maximum specified chi-square value were calculated for utilizing the main source of resources and level of sufficiency of library collection, also calculated the seasonal indices average method to rate the level of services provided by the college library. The faculty members working in MUMT have been selected randomly for the distribution of the questionnaire 200 questionnaire were distributed and 142 (71%) were returned after the completion. Out of 142 respondents 103 were males and 39 were females.

As shown in table I, majority of (38.73%) respondents are visiting library once in a week and 14(9.85%) respondents never go to library.

Table 1: Frequency of visiting library

Frequency	Respondent	Percentage
Daily	38	26.76
Ones in two days	35	24.64
Ones in week	55	38.73
Never	14	9.85
Total	142	100

Respondents were asked to what purpose they are seeking information. 78(54.92%) faculty members sought information for preparing class lectures, 62(43.66%) for keeping up date knowledge, 35(24.64%) for writing and presenting paper, 58(40.84%) for news and 18(12.67%) for guiding research scholars. It is observed that the number of faculty members who are using library facility for research purpose are very less in comparison with the other purpose.

Figure 1: Shows frequency of visit of faculty members in library.

Table 2: Purpose for seeking information

Purpose	Respondent	Percentage
For preparing lectures	78	54.92
Updating knowledge	62	43.66
For news	58	40.84
Writing research paper	35	24.64
To guide researchers	18	12.67

Majority of the respondents are seeking information for preparing lectures 78(54.92%) and updating knowledge 62(43.66%) and 35(24.64%) respondents

seeking the information for their research writing work. Faculty members were asked to indicate the type of information source which they used to seek information.

Figure 2: Shows the details of purpose for seeking information.

Table 3: Type of Information

Type of material	Numbers	Percentage
Text book	74	52.11
Journals	24	16.90
Newspapers	9	6.33
Research papers	11	7.74
Reference books	18	12.67
Govt. publications	6	4.22

Figure 3: Type of information seeking.

For seeking information, textbooks were the popular type of information source for all faculty members (52.11%). Sixteen point nine (16.90%) percent of faculty members use journals. Brown (1999) found that all of the scientists used textbooks, journals and monographs to support teaching activities.

Table 4: Internet facility at library and rated

Internet facility in institution rated as	Respondent	Percentage
Excellent	32	22.53
Good	76	53.52
Bad	19	13.38
Very bad	7	4.92
No facility	8	5.63

Figure 4: Rated by faculty members for internet facility available at the institution.

The internet is one of the most vital resources in any library, providing a crucial means for accessing the information needed. It serves as a gateway to a vast amount of data, enabling the easy sharing and acquisition of knowledge. In this information era internet plays an important role on providing lot of information 49(69.06%) faculty members are using internet daily while 9(6.33%) of the respondents are using the internet rarely.

Table 5: Barrier met seeking information in internet

Barrier in seeking information	Respondent	Percentage
Non-availability of related information	9	6.33
Inadequate knowledge to utilize internet	38	26.76
System may not be available	134	94.36
Server error	96	67.60
Information overload	128	90.14

Figure 5: Barrier in seeking information at the institution.

There are many factors involved on seeking information. These factors are being affected the information seeking behaviour of the respondents. Many times the respondent met the barrier of non-availability of required resources in the library. The majority of faculty members (90.14%) met the barrier on information overload, in this the respondents finding difficulty to get or collect the exact information what they want. 134 respondents (94.36%) meeting the problem while trying to seek information in internet, sufficient systems are not available.

1.6 Conclusions:

Research on the information-seeking behavior of faculty members in educational institutions is limited. This particular study did not aim to compare the behaviours of faculty members across different institutions. Given that the sample was chosen randomly, there is potential for further research in this field. Additionally, advancements in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are influencing how often faculty members visit the library his study provides

valuable insights into the information-seeking behaviours of faculty members at private engineering colleges in and around Chennai. It measured how often respondents visited the library, the time they spent there, the reasons for their visits, their primary sources of information, their memberships in other libraries, internet access, and the challenges they faced while seeking information. The study also evaluated the adequacy of the library's collection and services. To effectively utilize the available resources, user orientation programs are necessary. The wide availability of information on the World Wide Web is influencing the information-seeking behaviours of faculty members. As we transition into the digital information age, it is essential to offer comprehensive electronic resources to meet the information needs of users.

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